

to discuss the effect of ortho-substituents on the reaction mechanism. Although the polar effects of ortho-substituents are generally recognised to be equal to those of para-substituents, the ortho-substituents in some case produce a large rate-enhancement as was observed by Vankatasubramanian⁴. Jayaraman⁵ while investigating the proximity and cumulative effect in the chromic acid oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes has observed the rate retardation with ortho-substituents because of steric hindrance. But our results using KMnO_4 as an oxidant indicates a reverse trend viz. $o\text{-NO}_2 > p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2$ in nitro series and $2,6\text{-Cl}_2 > o\text{-Cl} > p\text{-Cl} > m\text{-Cl}$ in chloro series. This shows that steric hindrance is not of much importance. The plot of ΔH^\ddagger versus ΔS^\ddagger was linear with a slope equal to $\beta = 2401^\circ\text{K}$. This linear relationship indicates that all the substituted compounds studied follow the same type of mechanism. In order to find whether specific acid catalysis occurs, the experiments were conducted in concentrated H_2SO_4 and HClO_4 acid medium at different concentrations viz. 0.5 to 3.0M. The rate increases with increasing acid concentration and order with respect to H^+ is one upto 2.0 M. Bunnett's⁶ plot of $(\log k + \text{H}_0)$ versus $\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ gave a straight line with slope 'w' equal to 6.5. Bunnett formulated that the 'w' values lying between 3.1 to 6.8, suggest a mechanism involving water molecule acting as a proton transfer agent. This can be explained by the following mechanism.

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New Mannich Bases from 5-(Methylphenoxy)methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol 2-thione derivatives and their Bactericidal Properties

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THE herbicidal¹, bactericidal²⁻⁴ and insecticidal^{5,6} properties exhibited by oxadiazole compounds have made them of considerable interest specially in the field of pesticide chemistry. An effective insecticide based on oxadiazole moiety, against houseflies and cockroaches was patented⁷. Many Mannich bases have been reported to possess antibacterial⁸, fungicidal⁹ and anticonvulsant¹⁰ properties. In view of these observations a series of 3-arylamino-methyl-5-(methylphenoxy)methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol 2-thione derivatives have been synthesised to study their bactericidal properties.

The key intermediates 5-methylphenoxy-methyl 1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thiones prepared by the method of Young and Wood¹¹ were subjected to Mannich reaction according to procedure earlier reported in the literature^{12,13}.

The desired Mannich bases were isolated by two methods as described in the experimental.

The IR spectra of the Mannich bases showed the presence of C=S bands as sharp and strong peaks in the region of 1050-1090 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infra-red spectra were taken in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

5-(4-methylphenoxy)methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione (Ie)

A suspension of 0.1 mole of 4-methylphenoxy acetyl hydrazide, 0.1 mole of potassium hydroxide and 0.11 mole of carbon disulfide was refluxed on steam bath for 12 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled, solvent distilled off and residue dissolved in water and filtered. The clear filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the separated solid was crystallised from ethanol to afford the compound (Ie). The other two compounds (Ia, Ic) were similarly prepared (analytical data vide Table 1).

3-Hydroxymethyl-5(4-methylphenoxy)methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione (If)

To a suspension of compound (Ie; 0.1 mole) in 100 ml ethanol was added formaldehyde (40%; 1.0 g). The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature, the separated solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to furnish compound (If). Two other compounds (Ib, Id) were prepared according to the same procedure (analytical data vide Table 1).

NOTES

S.N.	Structure I				M.P. °C	Molecular formula*	Yield %
	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃			
a.	H	CH ₃	H	H	121	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	54
b.	CH ₂ OH	CH ₃	H	H	100-1	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	90
c.	H	H	CH ₃	H	96-7	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	50
d.	CH ₂ OH	H	CH ₃	H	79	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	87
e.	H	H	H	CH ₃	149	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	60
f.	CH ₂ OH	H	H	CH ₃	124	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	90

* Elemental analyses (N) were within ±0.4% of the theoretical value.

3-Substituted aminomethyl-5-(methyl phenoxymethyl)-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (II)

Method A: A solution of 3-hydroxymethyl-5-

methylphenoxymethyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione (0.01 mole) and aromatic amine (0.01 mole) in 25 ml of ethanol was kept overnight in a refrigerator. The separated solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol-acetone mixture.

Method B: To ethanolic solution of 5-methylphenoxymethyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione (0.01 mole) and formaldehyde (40%; 1 g), an ethanolic solution of aromatic amine (0.01 mole) was added slowly with stirring. The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 12 hours, when a colourless solid was obtained which was filtered and crystallised from excess ethanol.

Compounds(II) prepared according to these two methods are presented along with relevant data in Table 2.

Biological data

The compounds(II) as recorded in table 2 were

S. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Method	M.P. °C	Molecular formula ^f	Yield %	Antibacterial activity against*			
									<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. magaterum</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1.	Phenyl	CH ₃	H	H	B	141	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	65	-	+	++	+
2.	4-Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	H	H	A	152	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	65	+	+	++	++
3.	3-Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	H	H	A	105	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	56	+	+	++	++
4.	2-Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	H	H	B	110	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	58	+	+	+	+
5.	4-Bromophenyl	CH ₃	H	H	A	159-60	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	64	++	+	+	+
6.	4-Tolyl	CH ₃	H	H	A	148-49	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	60	+	++	+++	+
7.	2-Naphthyl	CH ₃	H	H	A	150	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	50	-	+	-	-
8.	4-Anisyl	CH ₃	H	H	B	127	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	58	+	+	++	+
9.	4-Nitrophenyl	CH ₃	H	H	A	140-1	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	56	-	-	+	+
10.	Phenyl		H	CH ₃	H	98	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	56	+	+	+	+
11.	4-Chlorophenyl	H	CH ₃	H	A	131	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	60	++	+	+	++
12.	4-Bromophenyl	H	CH ₃	H	B	129-30	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	62	+	+	++	+++
13.	4-Tolyl	H	CH ₃	H	A	132	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	61	++	+	+	++
14.	4-Anisyl	H	CH ₃	H	A	137	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	58	+	++	+	+
15.	4-Nitrophenyl	H	CH ₃	H	A	146	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	58	+	+	+	+++
16.	3-Nitrophenyl	H	CH ₃	H	B	148-49	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	54	+	-	+	++
17.	2-Naphthyl	H	CH ₃	H	A	144	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	50	-	-	-	+
18.	Phenyl	H	H	CH ₃	B	106-7	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	70	++	+	+++	+++
19.	4-Chlorophenyl	H	H	CH ₃	B	130-1	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	70	++	+	+++	+++
20.	3-Chlorophenyl	H	H	CH ₃	A	113-14	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	62	++	++	+	+++
21.	2-Chlorophenyl	H	H	CH ₃	A	115	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	60	+	+	+	++
22.	4-Bromophenyl	H	H	CH ₃	B	128	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	68	+	-	++	++
23.	4-Tolyl	H	H	CH ₃	B	85	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	68	+	++	++	+++
24.	2-Tolyl	H	H	CH ₃	A	151	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	60	++	-	++	++
25.	4-Anisyl	H	H	CH ₃	B	134	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	62	+	+	+	++
26.	4-Nitrophenyl	H	H	CH ₃	B	163	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	62	+	+	+	-
27.	3-Nitrophenyl	H	H	CH ₃	A	131-32	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S	58	+	-	-	-
28.	2-Naphthyl	H	H	CH ₃	A	110	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	55	-	-	-	-

^f=Elemental analyses (N) were within ±0.4% of the theoretical value.

- = No inhibition ; + = Zone size 6-8 mm ; ++ = Zone size 8-10 mm ; +++ = Zone size greater than 10 mm.

screened for their inhibitory effects against four organisms viz., *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus magaterium* by agar diffusion techniques¹⁴.

The agar medium was inoculated with a 24 hour old culture of the test organism. Filter paper discs (5 mm diameter) saturated with the test compounds (10 mg/ml in acetone) were placed on the agar plate after drying up the solvent. After an incubation period of 24 hours the zones of inhibition around the discs were measured (Table 2.)

Most of the compounds were found to exhibit activity. Significant activity against *S. aureus* was shown only by compound No. 12, 15, 18, 19, 20 and 23. Only three compounds (6, 18 and 19) showed marked inhibition against *Salmonella typhosa*. Bacterial cultures maintained at C.D.R.I., Lucknow were used.

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